

The Effect of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with Psychological Empowerment and Job Crafting as Intervening Variables

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Abstract

This research aims to calculate, analyze and describe the influence of (1) servant leadership towards psychological empowerment, (2) servant leadership towards work craft, (3) psychological empowerment towards innovative work behavior, (4) work craft towards innovative work behavior, and (5) servant leadership towards innovative work behavior. It also examines how psychological empowerment mediates the influence of servant leadership on work behavior innovation and the role of work craft in mediating the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior. The study results show that servant leadership has a significant direct effect on psychological empowerment, and Servant leadership has a significant direct effect on work craft. There is a positive influence of psychological empowerment on innovative work behavior.

1. Introduction

Currently, all aspects of life are required to compete to show the best because it is the best who will be able to survive to remain competitive in the changing demands of globalization. An institution should prepare itself to face the challenges in a world full of global turmoil. For example, the rapid development of world business has led to intense and tough market competition. Business actors produce and introduce their products daily with new creativity and innovation, so competition is inevitable. If business actors do not try to be innovative in producing their products, their business will be run over by other competitors.

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Not only that, but the role of human resources has also changed in line with the rapid progress of science and technology. Competition is becoming increasingly open, and the business environment is increasingly complex. Amid the complexity of global competition, creativity is an important factor for companies from various business sectors. The World Economic Forum has even predicted creativity as one of the skills (besides analytical thinking and active learning) companies need the most in 2022 (Ratcheva & Leopold, 2018).

In line with the previous opinion, La Prade & Wright (2019) stated that 61% of Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) from 64 different countries chose creativity as a characteristic that employees must possess in the future. Supporting the previous opinion, the survey results from International Business Machines (IBM) state that there is a need for workers who have digitalization skills and soft skills. Based on figure 1. in 2016, there were 12 core competencies sought by executives, and creativity ranked seventh (IBM, 2018).

Figure 1
Skills Needed for the 2018 Workforce
Source: IBM (2018)

For an employee, creativity can help improve the ability to carry out the tasks assigned and succeed in a career or job. Innovative employees will always come up with new ideas so that employees and the company can carry out their activities more effectively and efficiently. However, in the global realm, Indonesian society's innovation index is low compared to other countries.

Martin Prosperity Institute (2022) surveys assess a country's innovation based on technology, talent, and tolerance indicators. The innovative behavior of the Indonesian people is included in the lowest ranks. In line with the previous opinion, the Global Innovation Index (GII) ranks world economies based on their innovation capabilities.

Table 1. Indonesia's Creativity Index for 2019-2021

	GII	Innovation inputs	Innovation outputs
2021	87	87	84
2020	85	91	76
2019	85	87	78

Source: Global Innovation Index (2021)

Table 1. shows Indonesia's ranking for the last three years. It is seen that the availability of data and changes in the GII model framework affect the comparison of GII ratings from year to year. The statistical confidence interval for Indonesia's ranking in GII 2021 is between ranks 80 and 87. In 2021 Indonesia ranked 87th in innovation inputs, higher than last year but the same as 2019. For innovation output, Indonesia ranks 84th. This position is lower than in 2020 and 2019.

The description above illustrates that creativity is one of the behaviors that need to be considered by institutions, including banking institutions. The increasingly competitive and dynamic banking business has forced companies to constantly release new products and services to meet consumer demands in a rapidly changing world.(Prabowo et al., 2018). Therefore, innovative behavior is crucial for the company's success (Lu et al., 2015). The ability of businesses in urban areas (e.g., Jakarta and Bandung) to innovate and improve their products and services is a determining factor for economic and social growth (Maček & Starc-Peceny, 2019).

This study will examine innovative work behavior in banking institutions, namely the National Savings Bank (BTN). Quoted on the official website, currently, BTN has several competitive advantages, namely, the market leader in housing loans (KPR), focusing on the lower middle consumer segment, loans secured by high-value property collateral, a wide and unique distribution network, and high mortgage potential. But over time, in terms of home ownership loans (KPR), BTN has quite a worrying rival. Seeing the high public interest in applying for mortgages, banks in Indonesia are competing to offer their best products. There is no exception providing mortgage offers with relatively low or cheap interest rates, including BRI with a 5% interest rate, BTN 3.75%, Mandiri 3.72%, BCA 7%, and BJB 0.05% (per month)(Rumah. com, 2022).

The tight competition in banking institutions requires bank BTN to continue to maintain its focus on mortgages. The faster growth of the middle-class segment is a big market opportunity for Bank BTN's mortgage business. However, BTN cannot just sit on a low-interest rate policy if banking competition is getting tougher. BTN needs to innovate to increase product sales and services. Product and service innovation cannot be separated from the thinking of human resources in a company. Therefore, it is important to establish innovative work behavior for Bank BTN employees in facing banking competition.

The results of the Researcher's interview with representatives of bank BTN employees led to the result that innovative work behavior at bank BTN is still not paid attention to by the institution. This is reflected in the habits of employees in doing work based on procedures that have been carried out by seniors before. This is due to the lack of association between employees with one so that employees only have limited information and knowledge. In addition, employees are not open to the environment, and management tends to close themselves off. Another cause that makes it difficult for employees to provide innovation is that it is less participatory from employees.

Several previous studies have stated that the factors influence innovative work behavior are management factors such as leadership (Sutardi et al., 2021), organizational climate (Shanker & Farrell, 2017), organizational justice (Kim & Park, 2017), organizational culture (MA Khan et al., 2020) and some personal factors such as self-efficacy (Al & Teoh, 2022), psychological empowerment (Prabowo et al., 2018), craftwork (Afsar & Umrani, 2019), and personality (Li & Wang, 2017). To determine the factors experienced by bank BTN employees related to innovative work behavior, Researchers conducted an initial survey which was distributed to 60 respondents. The data from the survey are as follows.

Table 2. Factors Affecting Innovative Work Behavior

Factor	Statement	Percentage (%)	
		Yes	Not
Leadership	Leaders serve employees to develop innovation by being a mentor	31.7	68.3
Organizational Climate	Job descriptions are clear and structured	93.3	6.7
Organizational Justice	Managerial shows concern for employee rights	90	10
Self Efficacy	I can find a way out of the problem even though there are many obstacles	85	15
Psychological Empowerment	My opinion can be taken into consideration in the company's decision making	30	70
Work Craft	I organize my work in such a way as to ensure that I don't have to concentrate for too long	31.7	68.3
Personality	If I believe in an idea, nothing will stand in the way of making it happen	80	20

Source: Data processed By Researcher (2022)

Based on table 2. it is known that company leaders do not serve employees to develop innovation by becoming mentors, with a presentation of 68.3% "no" answers. Furthermore, judging from the organizational climate, the work is described clearly and structured, with 93.3% "yes" answers. The organizational justice factor shows that bank BTN employees feel managerial concern for employee rights with a 90% "yes" answer percentage. However, bank BTN employees' opinions are not considered in the company's decision-making. If left unchecked, this will have an impact on the weak psychological empowerment of bank BTN employees.

In addition, bank BTN employees pay less attention to the craft factor at work, and this is indicated by the answer "no" to the question, "I organize my work in such a way as to ensure that I don't have to concentrate too long." On the other hand, the personality of bank BTN employees is classified as a proactive personality where they will try to make an idea happen when they have an idea. It can be concluded from the results of this initial survey that the personality of bank BTN employees shows a proactive personality, but the lack of psychological empowerment, work craft, and effective leadership has an impact on low innovative work behavior. So this research will focus on three factors, namely leadership, innovative work behavior, and craftsmanship, to see their influence on innovative work behavior.

This factor was chosen because the respondent's answer was "No," so the achievement of these factors needed to be investigated to be able to agree with the results of previous research conducted by Prabowo et al. (2018), Afsar & Umrani (2019) and Khan et al. (2021).

Table 1. Leadership Style

Variable	Statement	Answer (%)	
		Yes	Not
Transformational	My boss once changed policies to increase organizational productivity	38.3	61.7

Transactional	I feel that my boss is more focused on transactional activities between individuals, management, and employees	38.3	61.7
Servant	My boss provides the best service for his employees	66.7	33.3
Situational	My leader makes policies according to the situation or incident	38.3	61.7
Authentic	My boss brings out his own genuine attitude by not following others	45	55

Source: Data processed by researchers (2022)

Based on the results of interviews with researchers with representatives of bank BTN employees, the leadership goes down directly in serving employees, such as motivating work-related and giving appreciation to the achievement of targets. Leaders also often hold training by inviting coaches who are competent in their fields. Although the leadership does not take the role of providing direct examples, in this case, mentoring, the company leaders still show their services to employees. This is evidenced by the attitude that cares about employee success, pays attention to employee needs, and management considers employees as partners, so they are treated with respect.

State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk or BTN in running its business is supported by human resources (HR), which are classified into several types of contracts, namely Permanent (7,912), Permanent ProHire (86), Permanent-Sekr (116), Permanent ExpHire (135), ProHire Contract (36), Permanent ExpHire (135), ODP Contract (137), SS PKWT (318), Permanent-teller (1274), Permanent-CSO (1264), MPP (88). The total number of employees as of January 2021 is 11,369 employees. The interesting thing is that in 2022 the number of millennial employees or those aged under 40 is very dominant, reaching 85% of the total number of current BTN employees. Therefore, BTN needs a special strategy for embracing employees, including the millennial group.

Figure 2. Graph of the Number of Millennial Employees

Source: Data Processed by Researchers (2022)

Popular perception says that millennial HR have impatient, self-important, and disloyal traits, which are traits seen from the organization's point of view. Some organizations believe that in order to develop and fully utilize the performance of superior human resources of productive age through

The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with Psychological Empowerment and Job Crafting as Intervening Variables
(MR Mahendri, D Susita, C Yohana)

the improvement of innovative work behavior, organizations need to change their rules and policies (Myers & Sadaghiani, 2010).

The leadership role is very important to ensure employees are motivated to achieve company goals and improve their company performance through innovative and adaptive behavior. Therefore, innovation is also needed from policymakers. Central bank leaders were asked to be observant in finding unconventional alternative solutions or Business As Usual. In looking for alternative solutions, decision-makers or leaders need to have innovative behavior, especially in responding to various challenges in the increasingly diverse global economy. A number of studies have found that servant leadership is positively related to employee creativity (de Lara, 2020; Yang et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019).

Servant leaders have a concern for their employees. They seek to empower, provide support, and meet the needs of employees. This can increase employee confidence in the leader and create a psychologically safe work environment (psychological safety). (Liden & Meuser, 2014). Employees feel that the risk associated with finding creative ideas is reduced, so they need a leader who can motivate them to show intellectual intelligence in creating creativity (Yang & Liu, 2019).

However, Newman & Tse (2017) shows that the relationship between servant leadership and innovative work behavior is not significant. These divergent findings suggest that there are psychological mechanisms that need to be investigated in order to understand how servant leadership affects employee creativity (Yang & Liu, 2019). Therefore, the inconsistency between previous research, which states that the independent variable can directly influence significantly on innovative work behavior, and previous research, which states that there is no significant effect of the independent variable, namely service leadership, on innovative work behavior, is a gap in this study.

Pratita & Salendu (2021) states that the relationship between the two variables is indirect and needs to be explained through additional variables, such as mediator variables. In their research, Pratita & Salendu (2021) used individual factors to improve innovative work behavior. In this study, the limitation of the problem focuses on two individual factors, namely, work craft and psychological empowerment. Therefore, psychological empowerment and work craft are used as intervening variables in this study.

The achievement of organizational goals is not feasible without empowering employees psychologically. This indicates that psychological empowerment is an important issue that needs to be researched. Empowered employees tend to find meaning in what they do, feeling that they have the capacity needed for their jobs. The form of empowerment needed by employees is related to training and development to deal with environmental uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity as a result of technological developments. Employees who engage in services also need assistance to overcome anxiety, excessive workload, and work stress. However, in its implementation, bank BTN only provides training regarding competencies, including auditing certification, and preparing certification for financial planners, credit analyst certification, and appraisal certification, especially for collateral price appraisers. There are only two soft skill empowerments at bank BTN: personality and discipline training. The monotony of this training cannot improve employee insights and ideas as well as the psychological well-being of bank BTN employees.

More precisely, the training is considered less effective in overcoming problems surrounding the psychological condition of bank BTN employees. In terms of service, bank BTN employees must have excellent conditions. With an excessive workload, and a lack of psychological empowerment, employees will experience fatigue at work; as a result, consumers are not satisfied with the excellent service provided by bank BTN, and in facing the challenges of the industry, employees will lack innovative ideas.

Another factor that makes researchers interested in job crafting. Craftwork presents an opportunity for the millennial workforce to integrate and organize work experiences into an

authentic sense of self. Work craft is an individual effort in aligning work experience with internal encouragement, which has an impact on self-development in aligning work experience and developing more intrinsic motivation, which can improve employee innovative work behavior. Especially for the millennial generation, employees are expected to be motivated to carve work experience into activities that support company performance.

The implementation of work crafts in the millennial generation is possible because this generation has flexibility in working. In fact, they think that they can change the existing work design. This happens because they see new opportunities that are more profitable for themselves. Millennial generation employees look for their own challenges in carrying out their work because millennial generation employees need to deal with challenges to be more motivated at work (Pradana & Suhariadi, 2020).

This work craft involves limiting the tasks of the job both physically and cognitively. Changes in task boundaries can be said that employees change the form or amount of activity when working, while changes in cognitive form can be in the form of how employees change their views on their work. (Rahmani Azizah, 2018). However, Bank BTN's work culture, which tends to be procedural and passive, makes employees not dare to simplify their work or change their views on the work process. Employees only become recipients of all the work assigned to them. If this continues to be experienced by millennial employees, it is likely that their intention to leave the company is due to boredom.

Several previous studies on innovative work behavior used respondents with work backgrounds as nurses (Carlucci & Schiuma, 2020), doctors (Al Wali & Teoh, 2022), and bank employees (Syahputra & Satrya, 2021). The novelty in this study is that researchers will describe innovative work behavior in bank BTN employees who are in the productive age (millennial generation). The title of this research is "The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior With Psychological Empowerment And Job Crafting As Intervening Variables."

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses quantitative research, which emphasizes testing theories by measuring research variables with numbers and requires data analysis with statistical procedures. The measuring instrument of this research is in the form of a questionnaire, the data obtained in the form of answers from Bank BTN employees to the statements submitted. The research method used is a survey method. The method is carried out with an approach to the type of descriptive and explanatory research so that the method used is a descriptive survey. This method was chosen to be implemented because, in this study, the Researcher looked for data by going directly to the field through a questionnaire. Through descriptive research, this study examines research variables through a more meaningful description of numbers and writings.

The model used in this study is causal modeling or relationship and influence, also known as path analysis. This model was chosen because in this study, the independent variable with the dependent variable there is mediation that affects. In this study, researchers used primary data for all variables, including independent variables, namely service leadership (X1), Psychological Empowerment (X2), and Work Craft (X3) as variables (intervening), and Innovative Work Behavior (Y) as dependent variables. This model was chosen because in this study, the independent variable with the dependent variable there is mediation that affects. In this study, researchers used primary data for all variables, including independent variables, namely service leadership (X1), Psychological Empowerment (X2), and Work Craft (X3) as intervening variables, and Innovative Work Behavior (Y) as independent variables also known as path analysis. This model was chosen because in this study,

The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with Psychological Empowerment and Job Crafting as Intervening Variables
(MR Mahendri, D Susita, C Yohana)

the independent variable with the dependent variable there is mediation that affects. In this study, researchers used primary data for all variables, including independent variables, namely service leadership (X1), Psychological Empowerment (X2), and Work Craft (X3) as intervening variables and Innovative Work Behavior (Y) as dependent variables.

3. Results and Discussions

Hypothesis Testing

After performing the PLS algorithm and bootstrap using SmartPLS 3.0, hypothesis testing can be conducted to test whether the proposed hypothesis is supported. Researchers tested the hypothesis by measuring the direct effect, which can be seen in the path coefficient and indirect effect, to see the effect of the intervening variables in this study.

1) Direct Effect

Table 3. Path Coefficient (*Path Coefficient*)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Servant Leadership -> Work Craft	0.979	0.980	0.004	22,662	0.000
Servant Leadership -> Psychological Empowerment	0.976	0.976	0.008	12,543	0.000
Servant leadership -> Innovative Work Behavior	0.256	0.264	0.087	2,955	0.003
Work Craft -> Innovative Work Behavior	0.536	0.521	0.096	5,605	0.000
Empowerment Psychology -> Innovative Work Behavior	0.205	0.213	0.085	2,404	0.017

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS 3.0 (2022)

H1: The Effect of Servant Leadership on Psychological Empowerment

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.976 on leadership serving psychological empowerment. This means that there is a positive influence on the serving leadership variable on the psychological empowerment variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 12,543, and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant direct effect on psychological empowerment. Therefore, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H2: The Effect of Servant Leadership on Work Craft

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.979 in service leadership to work craft. This means that there is a positive influence on the

service leadership variable on the work craft variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 22.662, and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that leadership service has a significant direct effect on work craft. Therefore, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H3: The Effect of Psychological Empowerment on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.205 on psychological empowerment to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on the psychological empowerment variable on the innovative work behavior variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 2.404, and the p-value is 0.017 (<0.05), which means that psychological empowerment has a significant direct effect on innovative work behavior. Therefore, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H4: The Effect of Work Crafts on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.536 on work craft to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on the work craft variable on the innovative work behavior variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 5.605 and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that work craft has a significant direct effect on innovative work behavior. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H5: The Effect of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.256 in serving leadership to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on the serving leadership variable on the innovative work behavior variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 2.955, and the p-value is 0.003 (<0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant direct effect on innovative work behavior. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

2) Indirect Effect

Table 4. Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Servant Leadership -> Empowerment Psychology -> Innovative Work Behavior	0.345	0.353	0.120	2,880	0.004
Servant Leadership -> Work Craft -> Innovative Work Behavior	0.589	0.577	0.086	6,820	0.000

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS 3.0 (2022)

H6: Empowerment Psychology Mediates Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above, the service leadership variable has an effect on innovative work behavior, with psychological empowerment acting as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is 0.345, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior with psychological empowerment as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 2.880, and the p-value is 0.004 (< 0.05), which means that the service leadership variable has a significant indirect effect on innovative work behavior, with psychological empowerment acting as a mediator. Therefore,

H7: Work Craft Mediates Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above, the service leadership variable has an effect on innovative work behavior with work craft that acts as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is 0.589, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior with work craft as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 6.820, and the p-value is 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that the service leadership variable has a significant indirect effect on innovative work behavior with work craft that acts as a mediator. Therefore,

*Discussion***H1: The Effect of Servant Leadership on Psychological Empowerment**

Based on the results of the hypothesis test statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient), it shows the original sample value of 0.976 on leadership serving to psychological empowerment has a significant effect. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 12,543, and the p-value is 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant direct effect on psychological empowerment. Medicate influence leadership serves to psychological empowerment of employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk is positive and significant.

J. Yang et al. (2019) mentioned servant leadership might significantly influence the psychological empowerment of employees by stimulating the potential of subordinates and building trust by serving others selflessly first. Servant leaders can provide developmental support and encouragement to their followers to develop new skills and achieve creative goals. Thus, servant leadership is positively related to the psychological empowerment of followers. Leaders who tend to have the ability to serve employees, in this case, welfare and other organizational concerns, affect psychological empowerment to improve four cognitions, namely competence, meaning, self-determination, and impact, needed by employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Baytok et al. (2019), Ghalavi & Nastiezaie (2020), and Tripathi et al. (2021).

H2: The Effect of Servant Leadership on Work Craft

Based on the results of the hypothesis test statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient), it shows the original sample value of 0.979 on leadership serving to work crafts. This means that there is a positive influence on the service leadership variable on the work craft variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 22.662, and the p-value is 0.000 (< 0.05), meaning that servant leadership significantly affects work craft. Medicate influence leadership serves

to Craft Work Employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk is positive and significant.

Craft work is always done by expanding the source of reference so that the source of structural and social work is expanded in the craft of work. Because it is employee-initiated, the work craft is more beneficial for both the employee and the organization (Hakanen et al., 2017). Servant leadership seeks to empower employees by involving them in decision-making, seeking their opinions, and praising them for their changes. Inspired by such an empowering environment, employees are expected to be able to enjoy their craft.

The usefulness of work craftsmanship for organizations makes it one of the organization's preferred approaches to motivating employees, and organizations actively assist employees in their efforts to engage in work craft behavior. One of the strategies available is the use of employee-centered leadership or servant leadership (Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2019). Servant leadership is expected to encourage work behavior among employees. Employees can enjoy such work behavior if they are empowered to do so.

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Bavik et al. (2018), Harju et al. (2018), and Jaya (2022).

H3: The Effect of Psychological Empowerment on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the hypothesis test results, the path coefficient statistical analysis in the table above shows the original sample value of 0.205 on psychological empowerment to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on the psychological empowerment variable on the innovative work behavior variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 2.404, and the p-value is 0.017 (<0.05), which means that psychological empowerment has a significant direct effect on innovative work behavior. Indicates the influence of Psychological Empowerment on Innovative Work Behavior of Employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk is positive and significant.

Javed et al. (2019) explained that the generation of innovative ideas is a non-routine task in which an individual must go beyond standard operating procedures with a sense of psychological empowerment and confidence, given all the support and means to implement those ideas. Furthermore, it is emphasized that empowered employees have more freedom to come up with unique ideas and are more confident that their ideas will be appreciated in the organization. Employees who have a sense of meaning and determination are intrinsically motivated to generate creative ideas. Furthermore, other psychological empowerment attributes such as competence, control, autonomy, and confidence to make an impact encourage employees to implement their ideas in the workplace.

Psychological empowerment, in this case, empowered employees to participate and stimulation them to issue innovative ideas in their work to be more effective in accordance with company goals, required by employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Javed et al. (2019), Singh & Sarkar (2019), and Rehman et al. (2019).

H4: The Effect of Work Crafts on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the results of the hypothesis test statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above, it shows the original sample value of 0.536 on work craft to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on the work craft variable on the innovative work behavior variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 5.605 and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05),

*The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with Psychological Empowerment and Job Crafting as Intervening Variables
(MR Mahendri, D Susita, C Yohana)*

which means that work craft has a direct significant effect on innovative work behavior. Indicates the effect of Work Craft on the Innovative Work Behavior of Employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk is positive and significant.

Employees have much more innovative minds. Traditionally, it is thought that resources come from management. There is currently an awareness that employees can increase their resources by engaging in work craft behaviors. Because employees can increase their resources and improve their innovative work behavior. The availability of additional resources can assist employees in both stages of innovative work behavior (Dediu et al., 2018).

Work craft involves employees changing certain aspects of the way they operate, interact with other employees, and how to think about their work (Kim et al., 2018). Positively, these actions can help employees to work better and enjoy work more. Innovative work behavior includes actions that are not normally rewarded but which still benefit the organization. It is possible that the more employees engage in craft activities, the more they will believe they can develop a creative new idea or task and implement it.

Work Craft is reflected in employees doing work in accordance with the existing SOPs in the company, and after the employees have innovations to do work more efficiently according to the needs to be achieved, this reflects innovative work behavior influenced by work by Employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Afshar et al. (2019), Bindl et al. (2019), and Pradana & Suhariadi (2020).

H5: The Effect of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the results of the statistical analysis of the path coefficient hypothesis, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.256 on service leadership to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on the serving leadership variable on the innovative work behavior variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 2.955 and the p-value is 0.003 (<0.05), meaning that servant leadership directly affects innovative work behavior. Indicates the influence of Servant Leadership on the Innovative Work Behavior of Employees of the Internal Audit Division of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk is positive and significant.

An important thrust of servant leadership is to serve stakeholders, and therefore, a servant leader sets an example for his employees to be "servant employees" who try to help the organization by involving himself in innovative activities. (Ahmad et al., 2021).

Innovation is multifaceted because it requires different individual tasks and behaviors at each stage, involving the generation, promotion, and implementation of new ideas. During this process, a person first comes up with an idea or solution to an identified problem. These ideas and solutions can be borrowed from various sources. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Zeng & Xu (2020), A. Iqbal et al. (2020), and Ahmad et al. (2021).

H6: Empowerment Psychology Mediates Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the results of the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the table above, the service leadership variable has an effect on innovative work behavior, with psychological empowerment acting as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is 0.345, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior with psychological empowerment as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 2.880, and the p-value is 0.004 (<0.05), meaning that the service leadership variable has a significant indirect effect on innovative work behavior, with psychological empowerment as a mediator.

Krog & Govender (2018) examine employee psychological empowerment as a mediator in the relationship between servant leadership and innovative work behavior. Their findings suggest that employee psychological empowerment mediates the relationship. With this theoretical basis and empirical evidence, the following hypothesis can be proposed. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by an et al. (2019) and Faraz et al. (2019).

H7: Work Craft Mediates Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on the results of the path coefficient statistical analysis hypothesis in the table above, the service leadership variable affects innovative work behavior with work craft that acts as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is 0.589, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior with work craft as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 6.820, and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that the service leadership variable has a significant indirect effect on innovative work behavior with work craft that acts as a mediator.

Research conducted by Xin et al. (2020) suggested that work craft behaviors were more likely to be transmitted from team leaders to team members because team leaders were closer to members and therefore team members could more easily imitate their behavior. Diligent behavior at work will synergize with the character of the leader who serves so as to create innovative work behavior.

Employees seek to increase their resources and challenges when they create their jobs. Because employees can make personal changes in their work, they find their work more enjoyable, thereby increasing the likelihood of engaging in psychological empowerment and work craft in extra-role behaviors. (Khan et al., 2021).

Khan et al. (2020) argue that servant leadership can trigger work craft behavior because the positive emotions associated facilitate employees in the cognitive processes required for idea creation. Thus, servant leadership, on the one hand, helps employees to be more proficient in generating ideas as it enhances positive emotions. On the other hand, through positive emotions and resource-enhancing roles, servant leadership enables employees to pursue innovative work behaviors. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Khan et al. (2020) and Khan et al. (2021).

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and hypothesis testing in the discussion presented, several conclusions can be obtained as follows:

1. The statistical analysis of the path coefficient shows the original sample value of 0.976 on leadership serving psychological empowerment. This means that there is a positive influence of servant leadership on psychological empowerment. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 12,543, and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant direct effect on psychological empowerment. Therefore, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study. It can be concluded that the first hypothesis of this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.
2. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.979 in service leadership to work craft. This means that there is a positive influence of servant leadership on work craftsmanship. In addition, it is shown that the t-statistic value is

*The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with Psychological Empowerment and Job Crafting as Intervening Variables
(MR Mahendri, D Susita, C Yohana)*

22.662, and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant direct effect on work craft. Therefore, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

3. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.205 on psychological empowerment to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on psychological empowerment on innovative work behavior. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value of 2.404 and p-value of 0.017 (<0.05) means that psychological empowerment has a significant direct effect on innovative work behavior. Therefore, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.
4. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.536 on work craft to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence on work craft on innovative work behavior. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 5.605 and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that work craft has a direct significant effect on innovative work behavior. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.
5. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.256 in servant leadership to innovative work behavior. This means that there is a positive influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value of 2.955 and p-value of 0.003 (<0.05) means that servant leadership directly affects innovative work behavior. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.
6. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above, servant leadership affects innovative work behavior, with psychological empowerment mediating between the two. The original sample value of the third influence is 0.345, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior with psychological empowerment as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 2.880, and the p-value is 0.004 (<0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant indirect effect on innovative work behavior, with psychological empowerment acting as a mediator. Therefore,
7. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above, servant leadership affects innovative work behavior with work craft that acts as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the third influence is 0.589, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of servant leadership on innovative work behavior with work craft as a mediator. Then, the t-statistic value is 6.820, and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that servant leadership has a significant indirect effect on innovative work behavior with work craft that acts as a mediator. Therefore, it is concluded that the seventh hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

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References

- Afsar, B., Masood, M., & Umrani, WA (2019). The role of job crafting and knowledge sharing on the effect of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior. *Personnel Review*.
- Afsar, B., Badir, Y., & Saeed, B. (2018). Transformational leadership and innovative work behavior. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 114(8), 1270–1300. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-05-2014-0152>
- Afsar, B., Masood, M., & Umrani, WA (2019). The role of job crafting and knowledge sharing on the effect of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior. *Personnel Review*, 48(5), 1186–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-04-2018-0133>
- Afsar, B., & Umrani, WA (2019). Transformational leadership and innovative work behavior: The role of motivation to learn, task complexity and innovation climate. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 23(3), 402–428. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-12-2018-0257>
- Ahmad, N., Scholz, M., Arshad, MZ, Jafri, SKA, Sabir, RI, Khan, WA, & Han, H. (2021). The inter-relation of corporate social responsibility at employee level, servant leadership, and innovative work behavior in the time of crisis from the healthcare sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4608), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18094608>
- Al Wali, J., Muthuveloo, R., & Teoh, AP (2022). Unraveling the nexus between creative self-efficacy, humble leadership, innovative work behavior and job performance amongst physicians in public hospitals. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*.
- Bavik, A., Bavik, YL, & Tang, PM (2018). Servant Leadership, Employee Job Crafting, and Citizenship Behaviors: A Cross-Level Investigation. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 58(4), 364–373. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1938965517719282>
- Baytok, A., Avan, A., & Zorlu, . (2019). The Effect of Servant Leadership on Psychological Empowerment and Organizational Identification. *letme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 11(1), 293–309.
- Carlucci, D., Mura, M., & Schiuma, G. (2020). FOSTERING EMPLOYEES' INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR IN HEALTHCARE ORGANISATIONS. In *Managing Knowledge, Absorptive Capacity and Innovation*, 185–212.
- Dediu, V., Leka, S., & Jain, A. (2018). Job demands, job resources and innovative work behaviour: A European Union Study. *European Journal of Work & Organizational Psychology*, 1–50. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2018.1444604>
- Faraz, NA, Mughal, MF, Ahmed, F., Raza, A., & Khalid Iqbal, M. (2019). The Impact of Servant Leadership on Employees' Innovative Work Behavior-Mediating Role of Psychological Empowerment. *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 5(3), 10–21. <https://doi.org/10.18775/ijmsba.1849-5664-5419.2014.53.1002>
- Ghalavi, Z., & Nastiezaie, N. (2020). Relationship of servant leadership and organizational citizenship behavior with mediation of psychological empowerment. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 89, 241–264. <https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2020.89.11>
- Hakanen, JJ, Seppälä, P., & Peeters, MCW (2017). High Job Demands, Still Engaged and Not Burned Out? The Role of Job Crafting. *International Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 24(4), 619–627. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12529-017-9638-3>
- Harju, LK, Schaufeli, WB, & Hakanen, JJ (2018). A multilevel study on servant leadership, job boredom and job crafting. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 33(1), 2–14. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-08-2016-0237>
- Iqbal, A., Latif, KF, & Ahmad, MS (2020). Servant leadership and employee innovative behaviour: exploring psychological pathways. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 41(6),

The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with Psychological Empowerment and Job Crafting as Intervening Variables
(MR Mahendri, D Susita, C Yohana)

- 813–827. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-11-2019-0474>
- Iqbal, Q., Ahmad, NH, Nasim, A., & Khan, SAR (2020). A moderated-mediation analysis of psychological empowerment: Sustainable leadership and sustainable performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 262, 121429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121429>
- Javed, B., Abdullah, I., Zaffar, MA, Haque, AU, & Rubab, U. (2019). Inclusive leadership and innovative work behavior: The role of psychological empowerment. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 25(4), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2018.50>
- Jaya, K. (2022). The Effect of Implementation of Servant Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Job Crafting and Employee Environmental Engagement as a Mediation Variable. *AGORA*, 10(1).
- Khan, MA, Ismail, FB, Hussain, A., & Alghazali, B. (2020). The Interplay of Leadership Styles, Innovative Work Behavior, Organizational Culture, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *SAGEOpen*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019898264>
- Khan, MM, Mubarak, S., & Islam, T. (2020). Leading the innovation: role of trust and job crafting as sequential mediators relating servant leadership and innovative work behavior. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, May 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-05-2020-0187>
- Khan, MM, Mubarik, MS, Islam, T., Rehman, A., Ahmed, SS, Khan, E., & Sohail, F. (2021). How servant leadership triggers innovative work behavior: exploring the sequential mediating role of psychological empowerment and job crafting. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, March. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-09-2020-0367>
- Kim, W. & Park, J. (2017). Examining structural relationships between work engagement, organizational procedural justice, knowledge sharing, and innovative work behavior for sustainable organizations. *Sustainability*, 9(205), 1–16.
- Kim, H., Im, J., Qu, H., & NamKoong, J. (2018). Antecedent and consequences of job crafting: an organizational level approach. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 30(3), 1863–1881. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-01-2017-0040>
- La Prade, A., Mertens, J., Moore, T., & Wright, A. (2019). The enterprise guide to closing the skills gap. IBM Corporation. In IBM Corporation. <https://www.voiced.edu.au/content/ngv:85596>
- Li, H., Shi, Y., Li, Y., Xing, Z., Wang, S., Ying, J., Zhang, M., & Sun, J. (2018). Relationship between nurse psychological empowerment and job satisfaction: A systematic review and meta-analysis. In *Journal of Advanced Nursing* (Vol. 74, Issue 6). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13549>
- Lichtenthaler, PW, & Fischbach, A. (2019). A meta-analysis on promotion- and prevention-focused job crafting. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 28(1), 30–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2018.1527767>
- Liden, RC, Wayne, SJ, Liao, C., & Meuser, JD (2014). Servant leadership and serving culture: Influence on individual and unit performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 57(5), 1434–1452.
- Lu, ACC, Gursoy, D., & Lu, CY (2015). Authenticity perceptions, brand equity and brand choice intention: The case of ethnic restaurants. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 50, 36–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2015.07.008>
- Maček, A., Ovin, R., & Starc-Peceny, U. (2019). Smart cities marketing and its conceptual grounds. *Naše Gospodarstvo/Our Economy*, 65(4), 110–116.
- Martin Prosperity Institute. (2022). Creativity and Prosperity: The Global Creativity Index. Group, Creative Class. <https://creativeclass.com/category/martin-prosperity-institute/>
- Myers, KK, & Sadaghiani, K. (2010). Millennials in the Workplace: A Communication Perspective on Millennials' Organizational Relationships and Performance. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 25(2), 225–238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-010-9172-7>
- Newman, A., Neesham, C., Manville, G., & Tse, HHM (2017). Examining the influence of servant and entrepreneurial leadership on the work outcomes of employees in social enterprises. *The*

- International Journal of Human Resource Management, 29(20), 2905–2926. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1359792>
- Newman, A., Schwarz, G., Cooper, B., & Sendjaya, S. (2017). How Servant Leadership Influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Roles of LMX, Empowerment, and Proactive Personality. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 145(1), 49–62. <http://10.0.3.239/s10551-015-2827-6%0Ahttp://ezproxy.hsutx.edu:2048/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=bft&AN=125205769&site=eds-live&scope=site>
- Prabowo, R., Mustika, MD, & Sjabadhyni, B. (2018). How a Leader Transforms Employees' Psychological Empowerment Into Innovative Work Behavior. *Psychological Research on Urban Society*, 1(2), 90. <https://doi.org/10.7454/proust.v1i2.32>
- Pradana, ER, & Suhariadi, F. (2020). The Effect Of Job Crafting On Innovative Behavior Through Mediation Work Engagement. *Airlangga Journal of Indonesian Management*, 1(1), 77–91. <https://doi.org/10.20473/ajim.v1i1.19402>
- Pratita, CP, & Salendu, A. (2021). Relationship between servant leadership style and employee creativity: The role of innovative culture as a mediator. *Journal of Ulayat Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.24854/jpu432>
- Rahmani Azizah, IZR (2018). The Relationship Between Job Crafting And Job Engagement To Generation Y Employees At The Head Office Of Pt. Bank Bukopin, Tbk Jakarta. *Empathy*, 7(2), 167–173.
- Ratcheva, VS, & Leopold, T. (2018). 5 Things To Know About The Future Of Jobs. *World Economic Forum*. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/09/future-of-jobs-2018-things-to-know/>
- Rehman, WU, Ahmad, M., Allen, MMC, Raziq, MM, & Riaz, A. (2019). High involvement HR systems and innovative work behaviour: the mediating role of psychological empowerment, and the moderating roles of manager and co-worker support. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 28(4), 525–535. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2019.1614563>
- Shanker, R., Bhanugopan, R., Van der Heijden, BI &, & Farrell, M. (2017). Organizational climate for innovation and organizational performance: The mediating effect of innovative work behavior. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 100, 67–70.
- Singh, M., & Sarkar, A. (2019). Role of psychological empowerment in the relationship between structural empowerment and innovative behavior. *Management Research Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-04-2018-0158>
- Sutardi, D., Nuryanti, Y., Ferdiyatomoko, D., Kumoro, C., Mariyanah, S., & Agistiawati, E. (2021). Innovative Work Behavior: A Strong Combination of Leadership , Learning , and Climate. *International Journal of Social and Management Studies*, 3(1), 290–301.
- Syahputra, NF, & Satrya, A. (2021). relationship between Work Ethic and Innovative Work Behavior Mediated by Person Organization Fit and Intrinsic Motivation on Banking Employees. In *Seventh Padang International Conference On Economics Education, Economics, Business and Management, Accounting and Entrepreneurship (PICEEBA 2021)*, (pp. 501-507).
- Tripathi, D., Priyadarshi, P., Kumar, P., & Kumar, S. (2021). Does servant leadership affect work role performance via knowledge sharing and psychological empowerment? *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 51(5), 792–812. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-10-2019-0159>
- Yang, J., Gu, J., & Liu, H. (2019). Servant leadership and employee creativity: The roles of psychological empowerment and work-family conflict. *Urrtent Psychology*, 38(6), 1417–1427. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-019-0161-3>
- Yang, J., Gu, J., & Liu, H. (2019). Servant leadership and employee creativity: The roles of psychological empowerment and work-family conflict. *Current Psychology*, 38(6), 1417–1427.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-019-0161-3>

Zeng, J., & Xu, G. (2020). How servant leadership motivates innovative behavior: A moderated mediation model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(13), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134753>